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**THE INCIDENCE OF MECONIUM STAINED
AMNIOTIC FLUID IN WOMEN DURING
LABOUR IN A TERTIARY HEALTH CARE
FACILITY OF KOLKATA, INDIA- AN
EXPERIMENTAL STUDY**Sourav Sarkar^{1*}, Saheli Misra², Sayantika Das³^{1*} Assistant Professor, COMJNM ,Medical College, Kalyani, India, contactdrsourav@gmail.com²Professor, Department of Pediatrics, ESIC PGISMR & Medical College, Joka, Kolkata, India³PhD Scholar, Department of Physiology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India^{1*} Assistant Professor, COMJNM ,Medical College, Kalyani, India, contactdrsourav@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

The occurrence of meconium has a direct correlation with fetal outcome. There are few studies regarding the importance of the consistency of meconium. Thus this study was done with an objective to find out the incidence of meconium stained amniotic fluid in women during labour in a tertiary health care facility of kolkata, India. This study showed the incidence of meconium stained liquor was 8.9% and incidence of meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) was 4.9%. The majority of the subjects in all the group belonged to either 25-30 years or below. In this study meconium stained liquor was observed in 65.6% primigravid mothers compared to 37.3% in control group showing distinct statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). In the MSL group 9.8% babies had meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS 3.9% babies had hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy(HIE) and 19.6% babies had transient tachypnea of new born (TTN).

Index Terms: Meconium stained liquor, Pregnancy, Fetus, Gestation, Neonatal disability**I. INTRODUCTION**

Meconium, the first gastrointestinal excretion by the fetus was named by Aristotle who derived it from Greek word 'opium', He believed that it was this substance that kept the baby sleeping in the mother's womb. 12% to 16% of term pregnancies are associated with meconium-stained liquor (MSL)⁵ which, in the vast majority of labour is not a cause of concern. However, in some circumstances, the passage of meconium *in utero* is associated with significant increases in perinatal morbidity and mortality. When the baby takes its first breath or during intrauterine gasping, the aspiration of meconium into the lungs, can result in a life-threatening disorder known as meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) and it is a leading cause of perinatal deaths¹. Meconium is the green viscous fluid that consists of fetal gastrointestinal secretions, cellular debris, mucus, blood, lanugo, and vernix. It first appears in the fetal ilium between 10 and 16 weeks of gestation². Passage of meconium in utero with staining of the amniotic fluid occurs in 12% to 16% of all deliveries⁴ and often is not associated with fetal distress or neonatal death or disability. Before 34 weeks of gestational age, meconium passage is rare⁹. Detection of meconium stained amniotic fluid during labour has become quite a challenging job for the health care providers. In one hand it creates panic and a state of dilemma in the obstetricians to decide the mode of delivery and on the other hand it puts stress on the pediatricians on the subsequent baby outcome following delivery. The consistency of meconium has a direct correlation with fetal outcome. There are few studies regarding the importance of the consistency of meconium⁶. Thus this study was done with an objective to find out the incidence of meconium stained amniotic fluid in women during labour in a tertiary health care facility of kolkata, India

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

This was a nonrandomized experimental study. After taking institutional ethical clearance and written consent from each subjects the study was performed during January 2014 to June 2015, study area was Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology at ESI-PGIMSR & ESIC Medical College, Joka, Kolkata, India. Subjects who had history of any of the following like any known congenital anomaly of the fetus, history of maternal heart disease, gestational diabetes mellitus, oligohydramnios and intrauterine growth restriction, severe Anaemia (Hb \leq 7gm/dl), multiple pregnancy, antepartum haemorrhage (APH) , malpresentation etc they had been excluded from final data evaluation. After maintaining exclusion criteria 102 pregnant women were selected from the same catchment area with the equal epidemiological background to exclude the social, ethical and racial variation on random basis. The sample size was calculated on the basis of the total annual deliveries in the institute. One hundred and two pregnant women were selected from the Indoor patients who had been admitted in the department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology during the period between January 2014 to June 2015. They were monitored in labour. They were divided into two equal groups of the same epidemiological background. Data were analysed by student t- test , Chi-square and Fischer's exact tests and p value below <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Microsoft excels and SPSS for windows were used for data presentation and statistical analysis.

III. RESULTS

Table 1: distribution of subjects according to age (years)

Group	Age(years)			Total
	<25	25-30	>30	
Control (n=51)	35.3%	49.0%	15.7%	100%
MSL (n=51)	47.1%	43.1%	9.8%	100%

The above table shows MSL found most in the age group below 25yrs in the study.

Table 2: distribution of subjects according to gravida

Group	Gravida			Total
	G1	G2	G3+	
Control (n=51)	37.3%	35.3%	27.4%	100%
MSL (n=51)	60.8%	35.3%	3.9%	100%

The table above depicts the frequency of MSL was found to be more in Primigravid mothers and less in higher gravid mothers.

Table 3: distribution of subjects according to gestational age (GA)

Group	GA (weeks)		TOTAL
	37-39	39.1-41	
Control (n=51)	56.9%	43.1%	100%
MSL (n=51)	58.8%	41.2%	100%

The above table shows occurrence of MSL was more prevalent in between 37- 39 weeks of gestation in comparison to the higher gestation age in this study.

Table 4: distribution of subjects according to onset of labour

Group	Onset of Labour		Total
	PGE2 Induction	SPONTANEOUS	
Control (n=51)	31.4%	68.6%	100%
MSL (n=51)	58.8%	41.2%	100%

Above table shows incidence of MSL to be more in cases who had undergone induction with PGE2 gel than who had spontaneous onset of labour.

Table 5: distribution of subjects according to baby's weight

Group	Weight (grams)			Total
	<2500	2500-3000	>3000	
Control (n=51)	13.7%	64.7%	21.6%	100%
MSL (n=51)	11.8%	74.5%	13.7%	100%

The study found maximum no of MSL in 2500-3000gm group in comparison to its incidence in < 2500gm and > 3000 gm babies in our study.

Figure 1: baby outcome

MAS: Meconium aspiration syndrome, **HIE:** Hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy

TTN: Transient tachypnea of new born

The figure shows the baby outcome in this study. Normal babies were given to mothers immediately following delivery. 33.3% with MSL were affected and required NICU admission.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study the incidence of meconium stained liquor was 8.9%, similar incidence are also reported in the study conducted by Rao, et al (2011) as 8.54% whereas Narang et al. (1993) found the incidence of MSL as 10.55% in their study. In table 1 age distribution of 102 subjects were analyzed in this study and it was seen that most of the pregnant women with MSL were below 25yrs of age. In MSL group it was 47.1%. This was followed by 43.1% of MSL group in 25-30 yrs age group. Therefore over all age distribution amongst the MSL group was 52% in the age group <25yrs and 36.27% in the age group between 25-30 yrs. In the control group of this study 35.3% were in the age group <25yrs and 49% were in the age group between 25-30yrs. Mundhra R et al. (2013), from their study found that MSL was 65.45% in between 20-30 years age group. P Gupta et al. 2014 from their

study found the incidence of moderate to thick MSL between 18-25 yrs of age group was 38.7% and above 25 yrs it was 19.4%. In table 2 gravida distribution of subjects were analyzed and it was seen that MSL was more in primigravida than multigravida . 60.8% in MSL group whereas 37.3% in control group were primigravid. Overall the frequency of MSL was found to be more (65.6%) in primigravida mothers. T. Surekha (2012) from their study also found that incidence of MSL was maximum in primigravida (71.66 %) followed by 21.67% were in second gravida, 5 % in third gravida and 1.67 % were in fourth gravida. In this study meconium stained liquor was observed in 65.6% primigravid mothers compared to 37.3% in control group showing distinct statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) indicating incidence of meconium possibility was more in nulliparous labour. 56.9% pregnant women in control group and 51.9% in both the meconium group had gestational age between 37-39 weeks at onset of labour whereas 43.1% pregnant women in control group and 48% in the meconium groups had gestational age between 39.1-41 weeks before going into labour. The study observed that prevalence of meconium (74.5%) was maximum amongst the babies of birth weight between 2500-3000gm whereas it was relatively less (11.8%) in healthy and constitutionally small babies of birth weight <2500gm. This points to the fact that incidence of meconium stained liquor was not always related to small babies only and was more dependent on physiological state of maturity or adverse response to ongoing hypoxia in any labour event. In the MSL group 9.8% babies had meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) 3.9% babies had hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) and 19.6% babies had transient tachypnea of new born (TTN). The effect of meconium on development of meconium aspiration syndrome and other co morbid state in the baby needs to be further critically analyzed separately and a long term study on these parameters should be carried out.

V. REFERENCES

1. Ahanya SN, Lakshmanan J, Morgan BL, Ross MG. Meconium passage in utero: mechanisms, consequences, and management. *Obstet Gynecol Surv* 2005; 60: 45-56.
2. Avery GB, Fletcher MA, MacDonald MG, editors. *Neonatology. pathophysiology and management of the newborn*. 4th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott, 1994.
3. *Indian Journal of Public Health*, Volume 59, Issue 2, April-June, 2015.
4. Mathews TG, Warshaw JB. Relevance of the gestational age distribution of meconium passage in utero ,*Pediatrics* 1979;64:301.
5. Maymon E, Chaim W, Furman B, Ghezzi F, Shoham Vardi I, Mazor M. Meconium stained amniotic fluid in very low risk pregnancies at term Gestation. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 1998; 80: 169-73.
6. Miller FC, Read JA. Intrapartum assessment of the postdate fetus. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1981;141:516-20.
7. Mundhra R, Agarwal M, Fetal outcome in meconium stained deliveries: *J Clin,Diagn Res.* 2013 Dec;7(12):2874-6
8. Narang A, Nair PMC, Bhakoo ON, Vashist K. Management of meconium stained amniotic fluid – A team approach. *Indian Pediatr* 1993; 30:9-13
9. Ostrea EM Jr, Naqvi M. The influence of gestational age on the ability of the fetus to pass meconium in utero. *Clinical implications. Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand* 1982;61:2757.
10. P Gupta, Amit Kaushik, S Chandra, CP Mishra, amniotic fluid characteristics and their co-relates among females delivering in a tertiary care hospital: a cross-sectional study:2014, *Indian J. Prev. Soc. Med.* Vol. 45 No. 1-2
11. Rao B, Chandrashekhar GS, Rao D, Hegde P, Ghate S V. Meconium stained amniotic fluid – A prospective study. *Karnataka Pediatric journal* 2011; 25(1):21-22.
12. Surekha tayade, the significance of meconium stained amniotic fluid – a cross sectional study in a rural setup; *IJBAR* (2012) 03(12)